

Evaluation of RES-H₂ hybrid energy system limitations operated in an Office Building at Central Greece

M. Taxiarchou^{1,*}, A. Peppas¹, A. Merkoureas-Karras¹, K. Tsoukalas¹

¹ School of Mining and Metallurgical Engineering, Laboratory of Metallurgy
National Technical University of Athens, Greece

ABSTRACT

The current paper provides a comprehensive investigation on the functional and thermodynamical limitations of a hybrid Renewable Energy Sources (RES) - Hydrogen (H₂) system. The main principle of this hybrid energy system is the combined utilization of different renewable energy sources in order to cover directly the various loads of an office-type building, while converting excessive energy production to H₂ chemical energy via water electrolysis. Finally, the produced gaseous H₂, which is compressed in storage tanks, is bound to be used at times of energy shortage to supply either a fuel cell or a H₂ burner to produce electrical or thermal power respectively. The prototype system is installed in an office building, located in the Attica region of Lavrion, appropriately renovated in order to host the hydrogen energy production and storage system. The system comprises two RES modules (photovoltaic panels and wind turbines), an alkaline water electrolyzer, a H₂ storage system (compressor, gas tanks), a PEM fuel cell and a H₂-burner. The building is equipped with various load types whose magnitudes and consumption patterns simulate those of a real office building. The operation of the whole site is conducted through an advanced Energy Management and Control System (EMCS). The outcome of this study reveals the limitations of the system, analyses the energy flow profile of building-RES integration and finally it highlights essential factors that need to be considered for future designing and implementation of RES-H₂ systems.

INTRODUCTION

The Building sector is a major contributor to Green House Gas (GHG) emissions as more than 40% of the total energy consumed in the EU is used to cover the needs for heating, cooling and electricity of buildings. Given the EC objectives of reducing GHG emissions by 20% until year 2020 and increasing the share of renewable energy, there is a call for the development of technological advances in the field of energy production, with a clear CO₂-free direction.

In this framework, the challenge as well as opportunity of the Building Sector is to move from fossil fuels based energy production to the use of renewable energy sources (RES) (solar, wind and hydro power where available) and clean fuels (hydrogen) to produce the required energy to cover the building energy needs.

The ongoing progress in the RES technologies, stumbles upon the obstacle of their intermittent nature, a characteristic which defines the usual fluctuations that they present in their availability, during a given period of time. The emerging solution to this major issue seems to be the storage of renewable energy in various stable forms such as electrochemical (rechargeable batteries), mechanical (pumped storage hydroelectricity, compressed air), electrical (capacitors) or chemical (power to gas, hydrogen (H₂)). The solution that has been applied mostly up to now is to store the excess of the produced energy in the form of electricity in large-scale batteries. The main disadvantages of this solution lie in the fact that large-scale storage batteries are generally expensive, have maintenance problems, limited lifespan, low density per volume (0.09 kWh/l) and high weight (0.03 kWh/kg), represent a considerable part of the cost of the whole system and contain hazardous chemicals and heavy metals that cannot be easily recycled and disposed. Moreover, the

energy provided in the form of electricity both by RES and batteries cannot be used in all cases to cover the various building loads.

In this framework, an intelligent, safe and zero CO₂ emission RES-H₂ hybrid system is examined using compressed Hydrogen both as an energy storage medium and as a green fuel. The main advantages that H₂ storage technology presents are the high energy density by molecular mass and the fact that the only by-product of H₂ combustion is water.

The transition to a hydrogen-based economy is nowadays a high priority in the research agenda of most developed societies, including EU, US and Japan, and intensive research is performed in this direction. Up to now, globally hydrogen is mainly used (about 95% of its applications) in “non-energy” or “indirect-energy” industrial applications (chemical, petrochemical, metallurgical, food, glass and electronics industry). The fact that hydrogen can be used as a pollution free energy carrier for transportation applications has attracted the interest of the automotive industry, which has made a significant progress in research and development in this area. Research on H₂ production, storage and use and renewable energy technologies is well advanced, although currently no commercial production of H₂ from RES exists in Europe. On the other hand, research on the application of these technologies in the building sector is at a very primitive stage.

In parallel with the advances in hydrogen technology, another trend that has dynamically entered the building sector is the development of the so called Zero Net Energy Buildings (ZEB), which will be able to generate from low-cost, locally available, non-polluting RES as much energy as their yearly load. A literature search indicated that there are other attempts to develop synergistic systems between RES and H₂ either through the use of simulation or with application in real buildings.

This paper presents the results from the development and operation of a RES-H₂ hybrid energy system during its application on an office building located in Lavrion Technological and Cultural Park (LTCP), Greece.

SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The implemented logic of the RES-H₂ system operation is based on the balance between the energy being produced and the energy being consumed which is managed by an intelligent Energy Management and Control System (EMCS). As can be seen in the following figure 1 the energy harvested from the 83 kW RES (Solar panels, wind generators) is directly used to cover the loads of an office building (525 m²). In case of excess energy, this is converted to gaseous H₂ by a PEM electrolyzer (22,3 kW) in order to be used as energy storage material. The gaseous H₂ is then compressed at 200 bar and stored in storage vessels. In case of energy shortage, the EMCS following its controlling algorithm can activate the trigeneration CHP (20 kW_{el} and 24 kW_{th}) and an H₂ burner (60kW_{th}), in order to cover the primary electrical and thermal needs of the building as defined by the user.

The EMCS role is not only to control the energy flow but also to monitor and regulate each component operational parameter to optimize the efficiency and to ensure the uninterrupted power supply of the building. EMSC is also supervising a Building Management System (BMS), which automatically monitors and controls all building operations in the most efficient way within the constraints of the hybrid system.

Another significant priority integrated in system control algorithm is the elimination of possible of hazards related to hydrogen handling, through communication with safety detection sensors which initiates a procedure for hydrogen equipment shut down and isolation of hydrogen storage, in case of an emergency.

The following figure 1 illustrates the EMCS interface.

Figure 1 Energy Management and Control System interface

The main characteristics of the RES- H₂ hybrid system main components are described in the following paragraphs:

1) Building

The prototype system is deployed in an office building of total surface 525 m² (Figure 2) which was appropriately renovated in order to host all necessary infrastructure. The building is divided in three main zones, the ground and the attic floor for office and meeting activities and a specially configured area which hosts the H₂ production, storage and consumption equipment.

The building incorporates a variety of electricity consuming equipment which could be enumerated as follows:

1. HVAC (heating, ventilation, and air conditioning)
2. VRV (Variable Refrigerant Volume)
3. Lighting
4. Other (Computing equipment & peripherals)

The consumption pattern (133kWh/m² annually, 30-57kW peak load depending on season) is representative of a typical office building operating Monday to Friday. The general outline is:

- Building lights turn on at 08:00 and turn off at 18:00
- HVAC turns on at 09:00 and turns off at 17:00
- Interior temperature setpoint is 21 oC (heating mode) and 26 oC (cooling mode)

Figure 2 Office building in Lavrion site

Heat pump/AHU - VRV

Two separate systems are used to cover the heating/cooling and ventilation needs of the two different heating/cooling zones of the building. The first one is based on the Variable Refrigerant Volume technology using 12 fan-coil units (maximum electrical load is approximately 25 kW). The second system is a combination of a heat pump with an Air Handling Unit (AHU) that is able to collect the thermal energy obtained from the heat recovery system (HRS) and to decrease the overall electrical energy consumption for heating, (32 kW maximum).

Lighting

For the interior lighting of the building, a total of 48 lighting fixtures, each with 2x36 W fluorescent bulbs are used, resulting in a total load of approximately 3.5 kW. A total of nine different lighting lines positioned in the optimum way in order to satisfy comfort levels and to minimize energy consumption through BMS control. Four halogen headlights, each consuming approximately 250 W, are also used to illuminate the exterior of the building during the night.

For the examined time period the average building load was 7,4 kW while the peak building load reached a value of 30,6 kW.

An indicative distribution of energy consumption divided in the four categories of building loads can be seen in figure 3:

Figure 3 Building energy consumption per load category.

As the above figure illustrates the highest consumption is related to the HVAC loads, which corresponds to 64% of the total building consumption.

2) Safety and Protection System (SPS)

Greek National legislation on hydrogen usage in residential buildings is very limited. Consequently, the safety and protection system designed for the RES-H₂ hybrid system was based on EU regulations and guidelines from the European Industrial Gases Association [EIGA] and the U.S. National Fire Protection Association (NFPA).

The SPS manages signals that are collected from different types of detectors and integrates safety measures and procedures that are initiated in case of alarm. The detectors have been mainly installed in the H₂ production, consumption and storage area.

Specifically, the following detectors have been installed:

- H₂ detectors to check for increased H₂ levels, indicating H₂ leakage
- Infrared flame detectors to check for fire fuelled by H₂, since this kind of fire can only be detected by the produced heat
- Smoke detectors to check for fire caused by other sources
- Heat sensors to monitor ambient temperature

For the rest of the building space, standard smoke and motion detectors have been also installed for safety and security reasons.

Depending on security level and in case that an alarm occurs, SPS through EMCS immediately initiates pre-configured procedures and informs the site manager for the event.

* Corresponding author, Email: ktsoukalas@metal.ntua.gr

3) RES

A RES park is installed in a nearby area, which includes:

- 624 photovoltaic (PV) thin-film CIGS panels (total panel area 475 m², total installed power 46.8 kW) facing South at an angle of 230, connected to 6 SMA Sunny Mini Central 8 000TL inverters.
- 6 wind turbines (downwind technology, blade diameter 5.5 m, total installed power 36 kW) equipped with a flexible blade system, which allows the blades to pitch and cone in high wind speeds and a bearing assembly, which allows the rotor to self-orientate around 3600, depending on wind direction and speed, connected to 6 SMA Windy Boy 6000A inverters

In order to ensure the uninterruptible energy supply of the whole system during insufficient RES production and limited hydrogen volume, it was decided to implement a grid-tied design which ensured also the release of the excess of energy to the public power network. The interaction of the energy with the grid allowed the calculation of the reduction on CO₂ emissions.

4) Electrolyzer

The electrolyzer initiates the water dissociation process when there is sufficient energy inflow from the renewables. The oxygen produced during the electrolysis is released to the environment for safety reasons.

The installed unit is a commercially available electrolyser (model G6HP) developed by ErreDue SLR. The current type of electrolyser is of alkaline technology, using a NaOH 20% w/w solution as electrolyte. The main technical characteristics of the electrolyser are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Installed electrolyser technical characteristics

Description	Unit	Value
Rated production capacity	Nm ³ /h	4.0
H ₂ outlet pressure	Bar	12
H ₂ purity	%vol	99.3 – 99.8
Operating environment temperature	°C	+5 to +35
Power supply	22.3 kW 3 Phase 400 VAC	

Before storage the hydrogen is purified in a DXH 12 (650 W) purifier system so as to meet the specifications of the fuel cell, which needs a minimum purity of 99.999%.

5) H₂ distribution and storage system.

The produced gaseous H₂ is distributed through 316m stainless steel pipes to the storage vessels. The main system components are the following:

- Buffers: Three bundles of 150lt water capacity, which serve as a temporary storage of produced H₂. They are placed between the electrolyzer and the end-storage vessels in order to moderate the pressure of inflowing gas, facilitating thus the compression to the permanent storage.
- Compressor (max 13.6kW): The applied control logic dictates that when the pressure inside the buffer storage cylinders (i.e. the compressor's inlet pressure) becomes higher than 6 bar the compressor starts its operation till the pressure drops below 1.8 bar.
- Storage: Next step is the storage of the compressed hydrogen at 12 commercial vessels of 50 lt water capacity each and 36 vessels of 80 lt capacity, all adding up to a total available space of 3480 lt.

6) Fuel cell

The micro-CHP prototype system was designed and developed by ICI CALDAIE based on commercial Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells (PEMFC) technology. The PEMFC installed uses two-coupled FCGEN 1300 (10 kW each) manufactured by Ballard resulting to a maximum of 20 kW electrical power. The electrical power is directed into an inverter where the direct current (DC) from the two FC stacks is converted to alternating current (AC) so it can be fed directly to a low voltage three-phase grid.

In addition, the micro-CHP used incorporates a heat recovery system able to collect and store the heat in a water tank 850lt volume. The thermal energy produced by the fuel cell (max. 24 kW_{th}) and according to demand, the water can be circulated, using appropriate piping and pumps, to the HVAC unit where through a plate heat exchanger the heat is obtained to pre-heat the HVAC and to therefore to reduce the electrical consumption.

In order to ensure the FC efficient operation and to limit the temperature below 55°C, which is the limit posed by the manufacturer; the system was supported by a chiller.

For the examined time period presented in this study and due to experimental design the micro-CHP Fuel Cell operated at a maximum power of 10 kW.

The system includes also peripheral components, which are essential for the operation of the micro-CHP unit:

An air blower which meets the requirements of the PEMFC by providing a maximum air flow rate of 1000 m³/h at 500 mbar. Humidifiers in order to achieve the required air humidity at FC stacks and a water demineralizer which is able to provide 60 litres/hour of demineralized and de-ionized water to the humidifiers.

7) Burner

The system also includes a prototype H₂ burner condensing boiler (60 kW_{th}) to convert the stored H₂ to thermal energy. The thermal energy produced by the H₂ Burner is also stored in the water tank described above.

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The evaluation of the performance of the system took place for a continuous time period of 192 hours during May 2012 for which the RES energy production was very limited. The selected period gave the opportunity to examine and evaluate system operation and performance under unfavorable RES availability.

The performance evaluation includes the calculation of each component's efficiency as well as the calculation of the overall efficiency of the H₂ system. It analyses the energy flows within the system and finally it concludes in the calculation of the energy equilibrium, which defines the amount of CO₂ reduction during this period.

RES Performance

The contributing power and net energy output of PV panels and wind turbines are measured by the EMCS system separately at rate of 1 min intervals. The PV panels presented limited energy output, reaching peak power values between 34-36 kW (figure 4). For the examined period the total energy contribution of solar energy amounted to 1889 kWh. The measured peak power values did not exceed a 78% of the nominal peak power. The contribution of the wind turbines was significantly lower than the PVs as during the 192 hours of the examined period produced only 206 kWh.

The total evaluation of RES contribution to the system revealed that the renewables produced a total amount of energy equal to 2094 kWh, with 1889 kWh or 90% originating from PVs and 206 kWh or 10% originating from wind turbines. A comparison between the two energy sources indicates that wind energy is characterized by more intermittent behavior than solar energy, at least for the time period examined.

* Corresponding author, Email: ktsoukalas@metal.ntua.gr

Figure 4 RES power output

Electrolyser efficiency:

The electrolyzer operated in start/stop cycles of 60 min duration minimum, and up to 2½ hours maximum in order to ensure the maximum lifetime expectancy. The largest part of energy available for this process is derived from PV panels and therefore there is an average daily span of 7 hours (10:00-17:00) where electrolysis takes place. The amount of hydrogen produced was measured firstly at the electrolysis stack and secondly at the high-pressure storage vessels.

The deviations observed between volumetric output of the electrolyzer and the stored quantities, account for a considerable non-usable volume of hydrogen. This amount of hydrogen is controlled releases to the environment and can be observed during the start up of the electrolysis where the quality of the hydrogen produced is very poor.

For a continuous operation of the electrolyzer for 300 minutes, it was calculated that the efficiency retained a steady value of approximately 52% taking into account that the electrolyzer consumed 99.95 kWh of electricity for producing 14.75 Nm³ of hydrogen while 0.4 Nm³ H₂ was released in the environment (figure 5). The energy produced is calculated by multiplying the produced hydrogen volume with the rated HHV of H₂ (12.7 MJ/m³). The specific yield value, which defines the energy consumed for the production of 1 Nm³ of H₂, was calculated to 6,78kWh/Nm³.

Figure5 Electrolyser efficiency

Finally it must be mentioned that the electrolysis unit incorporates certain peripheral devices, which consume energy even when there is no electrolysis process observed. The electrolyzer peripherals burden the system with a constant 1.4 kW and account for approximately 12-15% of the daily electrolyzer consumption, at least for the time period examined.

Compressor rate:

The average power demand of the compressor was 1.51 kW average while the maximum power demand was 2.62 kW. The operation of the compressor showed a significant peak during its startup where the compression rate was 6 Nm³/h but quickly descended to 2.6 Nm³/h. The capacity remained in this level throughout the whole compression process. The specific consumption of the compressor was calculated at 0.56 kWh/ Nm³.

Fuel Cell efficiency:

FC operation was mainly observed during early morning and night hours. It performed in average cycles of 57 min (although briefer or more extended cycles were recorded). The volumetric consumption of the FC at 10 kW was rated to 7.1 Nm³/h. The differences observed between the quantities of gas drawn from the storage and the quantities consumed, showed a significant volume of hydrogen released to the environment due to equipment constraints and operational procedures.

The electrical efficiency of the FC is calculated as the ratio of electrical energy output, to the chemical energy of the consumed H₂ (always based on HHV). According to the calculations performed for a production period of 155 minutes, the electrical efficiency reached a value of 47%. In terms of specific yield, meaning the amount of energy delivered per 1 Nm³, the cell stack is characterized by an average value of 1.658 kWh/ Nm³.

The difference of the amount of energy released by the stack and finally delivered to the building showed an average loss of 12.5%. This loss is mainly attributed to the inverter and wiring which resulted to an average AC yield is equal to 1.43 kWh/ Nm³.

In order to calculate the maximum value of the energy output that can be obtained from the CHP component, the thermal energy produced is calculated using the calorimetric equation (Equation 1):

$$Q=m \cdot C_p \cdot \Delta T$$

Where C_p is the specific heat of water, and ΔT is equal to the temperature change measured, inside the water tank, during each start/stop cycle of the fuel cell.

The heat output, for the same time period of 155 minutes, is measured to 23,73 kWh_{th}. As it can be seen in the following figure 6, the fuel cell consumed 14,18 Nm³ of hydrogen for producing 23,05 kW_{el} and 23,73 kW_{th} while 4,16 Nm³ of hydrogen was releases in the environment. Therefore, in terms of overall efficiency, a percentage of 93.5% is attained when the combined output (electrical and thermal) is taken into consideration.

Figure 6 Fuel cell efficiency

Overall efficiency of the system:

The overall efficiency of the RES- H₂ hybrid system is determined as the ratio of the energy produced by the CHP and finally delivered to the building, to the energy consumed by the system, for the selected time period. The theoretical value of the electricity that can be obtained from the additional volume of Hydrogen (19,83 Nm³) stored in the storage was taken also in consideration in the total amount of energy produced from the system. This volume is the difference of the amount of Hydrogen stored at the starting (t=0h) and at the ending (t=192h) point of the measurements.

The measured efficiency for the H₂ system for the examined period, taking into account all consumptions (including peripherals) and the AC output of the CHP, was calculated 11% approximately which can be reach 22% in case that all the amount of the thermal energy can be recovered on the HVAC system.

* Corresponding author, Email: ktsoukalas@metal.ntua.gr

The following figure 7 illustrates the energy flows within the system.

Figure 7: Energy flow diagram

Energy exchange with the utility grid

During the time period examined, the total amount of energy received by the grid accounted for 1127 kWh, while the total energy delivered to the grid amounted to 403 kWh. In a hypothetical scenario where the building was fully powered from the grid the total consumption is 1450 kWh so the RES-hybrid system managed to reduce the energy consumption to 724 kWh equal to a 50% reduction of greenhouse emissions.

SYSTEM LIMITATIONS

The performance evaluation presented in the previous paragraphs is now followed by specific limitations and drawbacks, concerning the overall performance of the system. Based on the specific yield of the electrolyser and the fuel cell as well as the consumption rate of the compressor, the electrical efficiency of the system is 11%. This low value is partly attributed to the energy consuming peripherals of the electrolyzer and the fuel cell, engineering room ventilation, which (most of them) operated continuously throughout the examined period.

The other factor, which contributes to the reduction of the electrical efficiency, is the control releases of H₂ from the electrolyser and the fuel cell which can be observed mainly during the startup of the equipment. Due to the specifications of the equipment significant amount of H₂ remains unused and it is released into the atmosphere. These losses amount for almost 27% of the total produced quantity, and in terms of energy loss, about 154 kWh of chemical energy (HHV) were lost.

The above considerations show that the optimum scenario for the equipment operation is to continuously keep the Electrolyser and the CHP to a standby condition and fully warmed up in order to minimize the Hydrogen releases. In this case the electrical efficiency can easily reach the value of 19 %

Finally it is observed that the consumption rate of H₂ is at least 35% greater than the production rate. This significant difference between the production and consumption rate of H₂ implies that a new sizing of the electrolyser could balance this difference and facilitate the operation of the system.

CONCLUSIONS

The current work constitutes an assessment on the performance of a RES- H₂ hybrid energy system, adjusted to cover the energy needs of an office-type building. The assessment was followed by an analysis on the limitations that emerge from this study.

The system is characterized by excellent coordination between its constituent parts (no failures observed), satisfactory efficiencies of all the involved equipment, and a well organized data acquisition system, which was vital for conducting the necessary measurements.

Special emphasis was given to the factors that affect the performance of the system. It was noted that the efficiency of the H₂ system is significantly reduced by the peripherals of the electrolyzer and the fuel cell. In addition the releases of H₂ quantity through the process of production and distribution also resulted in a significant reduction of the overall system's efficiency. The system designates itself as a fully developed near zero energy building, which offers prospect for further study throughout an extended period of time.

The quantification of all the operational parameters showed that the system can be easily transformed to a stand alone off grid system supported by a small battery bank which would cover the primary loads and the CHP startup. Future research activities are needed for the optimization of RES-H₂ hybrid systems as they present significant potential. RES-H₂ hybrid systems can effectively address the intermittent nature of RES, they can facilitate the effective integration of RES in building environment and they can place the building sector in the driving seat of the efforts for sustainable development.

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* Corresponding author, Email: ktsoukalas@metal.ntua.gr